

Archaeology Data Service: Transforming the Accessibility and (Re-)Usability of Archaeological Training Resources

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The [Archaeology Data Service](#) (ADS) is the leading accredited digital repository for archaeology and heritage data generated by UK-based fieldwork and research. Founded in 1996, the core activity of the ADS is the long-term digital preservation of data entrusted to its care from both industry and academia. Although primarily an organisation that serves the archaeology sector, the ADS is connected to, and interacts with, an interdisciplinary network of people and organisations across Europe.

The ADS is committed to preserving and disseminating data under its stewardship in accordance with the FAIR data principles (for findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable assets) ([Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016](#)), ensuring that these valuable digital resources are available to support knowledge discovery and innovation for the archaeology and heritage community and beyond. As such, all resources archived with the ADS are provided open access and delivered through its website to facilitate reuse by the heritage sector and wider community.

The ADS’s commitment to openness extends beyond its collections to sharing its expertise with organisations across the UK and Europe. It collaborates on large-scale research projects, provides training in digital preservation and data management, and publishes its well-established and long-running [Guides to Good Practice \(G2GP\)](#). G2GP is collaborative documentation that has been created by digital preservation experts and archaeological specialists to provide best practices for managing digital archaeological materials.

Dr Nicky Garland is Training and Communications Manager at the ADS, based at the University of York. He is also an Expert-in-Residence in the 2024 cohort of The Turing Way Practitioners Hub. Dr Garland says: “Despite the ADS’ commitment to openness, we have identified a key gap in our practice – namely that our training and guidance materials are not currently shared in an open, accessible and reproducible way. ADS training resources are currently only shared with participants and internally with colleagues, and the widely cited G2GP have evolved over the last 30 years from a print to web format, which is currently difficult to navigate and not searchable.”

This case study describes the ADS’s initiative to align these valuable knowledge resources with its core values by making them fully open and FAIR for wider dissemination. The organisation will accomplish this by 1) updating the existing G2GP to a new format to make them more findable, accessible and reusable, as well as authoring several new guides in this format; and 2) creating a

portal for training resources produced and shared by the ADS.

Turning Training Guides into Open Educational Resources

The ADS aims to transform its training resources and the G2GP into Open Educational Resources (OERs) to enhance their accessibility and reusability, and ultimately enhance digital preservation practice within the heritage sector. According to [UNESCO \(2022\)](#), OERs are “learning, teaching and research materials in any format and medium . . . that have been released under an open license, permitting no-cost access, re-use, re-purposing, adaptation, and redistribution by others”.

Several Arts and Humanities organisations in Europe have successfully adopted OER practices, including European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) projects such as [DARIAH Campus](#), demonstrating the effectiveness of this approach. Adopting this approach in the ADS will ensure that key resources are freely accessible, fostering greater digital preservation and knowledge-sharing across the sector. This aligns with UNESCO’s Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) – particularly in Quality Education (SDG 4), Gender Equality, Industry Innovation and Infrastructure, Reduced Inequalities, and Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions.

To achieve this transformation, the ADS implemented a comprehensive roadmap to:

- make key training resources and the G2GP freely available for reuse, adaptation and repurposing
- adopt appropriate open licences in alignment with ADS policies and values
- assign persistent identifiers to ensure better discoverability and long-term accessibility
- update materials into an accessible, open-source format to support reproducibility and sustainability
- ensure materials are open and freely available, reinforcing the ADS’s commitment to equitable access and long-term digital preservation in the archaeology sector and beyond.

Tailored Approaches: Interactive Guides and a New Portal

“To transform our resources into open-access materials,” says Dr Garland, “we implemented two technical approaches, each of which was tailored to our different resource types: a new format for our G2GP and a custom Training Portal for our educational resources. Both solutions were designed with FAIR principles at their core, enabling us to share our expertise more effectively with the wider heritage community.”

Guides to Good Practice

The ADS selected [Jupyter Book](#) as its new format for the G2GP after a thorough evaluation of technologies adopted by similar communities of practice – most notably *The Turing Way*.

This format offers several key advantages for the organisation’s users:

- enhanced searchability and logical organisation of content

- the readable presentation across devices
- ability to export to various formats (for example, PDF or EPUB) for offline use
- source material examples that can be executed and modified by users.

Each guide is now allocated, for the first time, a persistent identifier (Digital Object Identifier, or DOI) and a full citation format, ensuring proper attribution for those who utilise and cite these resources. By sharing not just the content but also the source code for the G2GP, the ADS enables others to make a personal copy (fork of the GitHub repository) and create their own guides based on original ADS content, truly embracing the spirit of OERs.

Implementation began with a pilot conversion of the [Aerial Survey Guide to Good Practice](#), which allowed the ADS to refine its approach before expanding to other guides. This approach was subsequently adopted for a newly created [Marine Survey Data Guide](#), which now has its own DOI (Groom, D. and Niven, K. 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5284/3y3w-g262>), developed as part of the AHRC-funded [Unpath'd Waters Project](#).

Training Portal

For its diverse training materials, the ADS has developed a custom Training Portal, which will be accessible via the organisation's website. The Portal's architecture was inspired by successful platforms such as DARIAH Campus but tailored to meet the specific needs of the archaeological user community. Jamie Bradley, ADS Lead Software Developer, undertook the development, with the platform tested across the organisation before public release.

To ensure that these resources can be defined as OERs, each resource in the Training Portal includes:

- Description of resource
- Link to resource
- Contributors and Author(s)
- Persistent identifier (a DOI minted by the ADS)
- Full citation (to copy for citation purposes)
- Open licence attribution (in most cases Creative Commons CC BY 4.0).

Dr Garland says: "This structured approach ensures that our training resources not only meet accessibility standards but are properly documented and credited, and are trackable in terms of their impact and reuse via the DOI."

"Several resources have been prepared in this format and are ready for publication once the platform is launched later in 2025. We are actively seeking additional sources to expand the Portal both from staff members within the ADS and our key collaborators. Some of the upcoming resources include instructional videos on metadata fundamentals for beginners, documentation of the ADS Archiving Workflow, and curated heritage datasets suitable for undergraduate and graduate-level research projects."

Choosing the Right Platform and Gaining Institutional Buy-in

As a long-standing initiative, the ADS – and particularly the G2GP – faced challenges in ensuring that any new solution would be robust, future-proof, and widely accepted within the organisation.

One challenge was securing organisational buy-in. Given the historical significance of G2GP, it was essential to demonstrate that transitioning to a new format would provide long-term stability rather than introduce short-lived technological shifts. Internal advocacy was key, and insights from *The Turing Way* community helped team members effectively communicate the benefits of open, modular and adaptable formats.

Additionally, the technical sustainability of the guides was a concern. Since their inception in 1997, G2GP materials have undergone multiple transformations – from print to a wiki-based system, and later to WordPress-hosted web pages. Each transition included workload challenges and risked content loss, compatibility issues, and burdens in maintaining a new system.

“To address this,” says Dr Garland, “we selected Jupyter Books as our new publishing format, using Markdown-based chapters. This approach ensures that the content remains format-agnostic, making future transitions easier and that the materials can be openly accessible and version-controlled via a GitHub repository. By adopting this approach, we ensure that the G2GP remains adaptable, sustainable, and open for future generations.”

Next steps: Expansion, Promotion, and FAIR Implementation

The next steps for G2GP involve exploring the consequences of migrating Marine Survey Data resources to [Jupyter Book 2.0](#). Following this we will:

- Expand this Jupyter Book format to all existing G2GP.
- Adopt this format for future guides – particularly those developed under the new AHRC-funded [Heritage Science Data Service](#).
- Update older guides (some dating back to 1998) to ensure both content and format are modernised.
- Launch a communications campaign to promote the transition and highlight how this approach improves FAIR principles.

In early 2025, ADS will launch its Training Portal to provide OERs through the ADS website. This Portal will feature:

- a Jupyter Book Guide to Data Management for Researchers, with source materials openly available via the [ADS Organisation Github account](#)
- a commitment to publishing one new training resource per quarter
- exploration of GitHub-based collaboration, enabling community contributions – similar to *The Turing Way* and The Carpentries models
- exploring metadata requirements and controlled vocabularies for OERs to make these resources more interoperable with existing digital catalogues.

As part of EU-funded research projects (such as [ATRIUM](#) and [ECHOES](#)), the ADS aims to implement a FAIR-by-design methodology for all ADS training materials. This approach, successfully

used in other disciplines (Garcia et al., 2020), will ensure that ADS resources meet the highest standards for accessibility, interoperability, and long-term usability.

Dr Garland says: “Organising our data in this manner and ensuring it is open and accessible to others is also the first step to enabling future projects that may utilise AI, enhancing the offering of these guides and training resources in more bespoke ways for different organisations that utilise the services of the ADS. The sessions provided within The Turing Way Practitioners Hub have provided the structure and guidance for the ADS to explore avenues into AI in the future in an open and ethical manner.”

Call to Action

The ADS invites the community to:

- explore and contribute to its GitHub-hosted guides and training resources
- collaborate on developing new OERs
- provide feedback on the transition to Jupyter Books and FAIR principles.

If you are interested in partnering with ADS or contributing to this initiative, please reach out to help@archaeologydataservice.ac.uk, as the organisation welcomes collaboration.

Key Takeaways

- The ADS is committed to transforming its training materials and G2GP into OERs that align with FAIR principles. This will improve discoverability, accessibility and reusability, fostering digital preservation and knowledge sharing within the heritage sector.
- Adoption of Jupyter Books for G2GP will enhance management, searchability and logical presentation of ADS’ rich set of resources, with Jupyter notebooks that can be executed and modified by users.
- The launch of a new Training Portal in 2025 will provide structured, openly licensed materials with persistent identifiers. Each resource with metadata information including description, DOI, authors and citation will improve the acknowledgement of resource developers and reusability by new users.
- Key to the success of the project was securing organisational buy-in – achieved through evidence of benefits, internal advocacy, and insights from community resources such as *The Turing Way*.
- By transitioning from legacy formats, the ADS is ensuring the long-term accessibility and adaptability of its resources. This work paves the way for AI-driven applications in the future, such as personalised learning experiences for archaeologists.

Expert in Residence Spotlight: Dr. Nicky Garland

Dr. Nicky Garland is the ADS Training and Communications Manager. Nicky is an archaeologist with a background in the Iron Age and Roman Britain, archaeological theory, and digital approaches to the past. He worked in developer-funded archaeology in the UK and Ireland for more than a

decade before completing doctoral research at the UCL Institute of Archaeology. Nicky has extensive experience in teaching and training in both developer-led archaeology and academia and now leads ADS's training and communications efforts.

Highlights from *The Turing Way Practitioners Hub*

“Participating in The Turing Way Practitioners Hub provided us with an opportunity to engage with other organisations across various sectors to foster collaboration and knowledge-sharing. By joining the events we were able to connect with other participants and gain insights from real-world applications to shape changes in open-source, open-data, and other best practices within our own organisation. Part of the impact of the Practitioners Hub came from learning from the organisers themselves, members of *The Turing Way* community, and the example provided by collaborative and open resources such as *The Turing Way* handbook.”

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The Turing Way Practitioners Hub's 2024-25 Cohort was co-delivered by Dr **Malvika Sharan**, Senior Researcher - Open Research and **Arielle Bennett**, Senior Researcher - Open Source Practices. **Stuart Gillespie** is the technical writer for this case study, and others in the series. **Léllé Demertzi** is the Research Project Manager.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of 'Experts in Residence' across partnering organisations.

For any comments, questions or collaboration with *The Turing Way*, please email: turing-way@turing.ac.uk.

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